

INVESTMENTS AS A CRITICAL FACTOR IN AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

Nadirov Khurshid Hamza ugli

JSCB "Agrobank" Department financing of agro-industrial complex enterprises
Leading specialist

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13319219>

Agriculture is a critical sector of the economy of any country. At the present stage, agriculture in our country is in difficult situation due to existing unresolved problems associated with the lack of tangible support from the state, shortage of competent, experienced and high qualified personnel, promising and young specialists, lack of finance, underdeveloped infrastructure, etc. To solve most problems, an influx of funds in the form of investments is required. Investments in agriculture and agricultural assets are very important in promoting sustainable agricultural production and the country's potential.

Keywords: Agriculture, investments, government support.

Introduction. The problem of investments has been widely studied by the world community for a long time. It is investments that are a necessary condition for the stable functioning and development of economic entities, economic sectors, municipalities, regions, and the state as a whole [5]. Investments are a relatively new category for the Uzbek economy. Investments are understood as "money, securities, and other property, including property rights and other rights that have a monetary value, invested in objects of entrepreneurial and other activities in order to make a profit or achieve another useful effect". Investments as an economic category perform a number of important functions at both macroeconomic and microeconomic levels. At the macroeconomic level, investments are the basis for implementing the policy of expanded reproduction, accelerating scientific and technological progress, improving the quality of goods and services, ensuring their competitiveness, structural restructuring of the economy and balanced development of all its sectors, the functioning of financial markets, the banking sector, implementing social policy, and ensuring the national security of the country [1].

At the microeconomic level, investments provide solutions to such problems as the creation of fixed assets, reconstruction and expansion of existing enterprises, their technical re-equipment, ensuring a stable financial condition and maximizing the profits of an economic entity, ensuring the competitiveness of manufactured products, etc [3].

As for the industry called agriculture, investing in agriculture is one of the most effective ways to increase agricultural productivity, reduce poverty levels

and improve environmental sustainability. The transition to sustainable agriculture is impossible without significant new investments aimed at preserving natural resources and increasing the efficiency of their use and reducing losses at all stages of production, processing and consumption.

The necessary elements for all agricultural investors and rural entrepreneurs to mobilize resources and take on the significant risks associated with agricultural investment are good governance, macroeconomic stability, rural infrastructure, protection of poverty rights and effective market institutions. Investing in agriculture for a better future means more than just accumulating physical capital in the sector, it will require building the institutions and human capacity that will enable the agricultural sector to contribute to sustainable development [4].

Foreign direct investment in Agriculture.

In recent years, much attention has been paid to foreign direct investment, which, for example, is a growing source of investment in agriculture in low- and middle-income countries. However, FDI in agriculture remains very small compared to domestic investment in agriculture. FDI is unlikely to make a significant contribution to increasing agricultural capital stock, but it can have a significant impact at the local level. FDI in agriculture can create an environment that is promising for job creation and technology transfer, but has potential negative social and environmental consequences remain a matter of concern [4].

Private investment. Private investment implies investments made by non-state enterprises and organizations, as well as investments of individuals. This type of investment in agriculture plays an important role. Private investment is fundamental to meeting future growth in demand, achieving food security and transitioning to sustainable agriculture [2].

Government spending on agriculture. Following investments in fixed assets directly from the farms themselves, the second largest source of investment in agriculture is government spending. Public investments include investments of financial resources from the federal budget, budgets of constituent entities of Uzbekistan, state extra-budgetary funds directed to the creation, development and maintenance of enterprises and organizations related to the state property, the implementation of target programs and priority investment projects [4].

Government spending is a vital component of creating a favorable climate for investment in farms and is positively correlated with the formation of the required volume of fixed assets of farms for each worker. Public investment in agriculture is necessary to stimulate the quantitative growth of private

investment and ensure its economic and social orientation. However, as governments in all regions face financial constraints and the need to meet the needs of all sectors, they must make difficult decisions when allocating public resources.

In order for private sectors to have new opportunities to invest in agriculture, a clear understanding of the incentives and constraints they face in different contexts is necessary. The public sector plays an indispensable role in creating and stimulating a favorable investment can occur with socially beneficial results. Government spending on agriculture has an overwhelming positive impact on sector productivity.

Farmers invest in their farms by purchasing agricultural machinery and equipment, purchasing or caring for animals until they reach productive age, growing crops over a long period of time, improving the quality of their land, and constructing agricultural buildings. Governments can invest in, among other things, the construction and operation of rural roads and large-scale irrigation systems, assets that produce productivity results over a long period of time.

Governments are making large investments in agricultural research and development, which generate intellectual capital that is a critical contribution to improving long-term agricultural productivity. Both governments and individuals invest in education, which increases the productivity of those who receive it and generates long-term returns through the development of human capabilities.

Farmers spend time and resources organizing producer associations, which are a form of social capital that reduces risk and increases productivity. All of these activities are types of investment because they accumulate capital.

Creating a favorable climate for investment in agriculture. The question of what factors create the right climate for private investment has received considerable attention recently. Less attention has been paid to the importance of these factors when investing in agriculture. Overall, the investment climate plays a central role in reducing poverty levels and achieving growth and stability.

The investment climate reflects many area-specific factors that provide opportunities and incentives for companies to invest effectively, create jobs, and expand their operations. A good investment climate involves more than just making a profit for companies; if that were the goal, it would be enough to limit costs and risks to a minimum. A good investment climate improves performance for society as a whole [6].

According to the concept of the World Bank, the functions of the state to ensure a generally favorable investment climate are as follows:

- Ensuring stability and security, including respect for rights to land resources and other property, compliance with contractual obligations and reducing crime;
- Improving the regulatory and taxation regime both within countries and at their borders;
- Creation of infrastructure and formation of financial market institutions;
- Promoting the labor market through job training, developing flexible and fair labor regulations, and helping working people adapt to change.

Sustainable agricultural growth depends on policies that extend beyond the agricultural sector to address issues that governments can improve the environment for investment in agriculture. Briefly those problems look like this:

Investment policy. Transparency of laws and regulations, ownership of land and other assets, protection of intellectual property and enforcement of contracts. Promotion of investments and facilitation of the investment regime. Institutions and policies that promote investment in agriculture, technology transfer to local farmers, and public-private collaboration. Human resource development and skills development. Human resource development, training of local farmers and opportunities for local research and capacity building.

Trade policy. Customs and administrative procedures, trade policy impact assessment, export promotion and financing, regional trade agreements.

Environment. Policies for natural resource management and the introduction of cleaner technologies, integration of R&D with the environmental policies, energy needs and mitigation of adverse weather conditions.

Responsible management. Labor standards in agriculture, respect for human rights, environmental protection, labor relations and financial reporting.

Infrastructure development. Harmonious infrastructure, rural development and agricultural policies, transparent allocation procedures, information and communication technologies for agriculture, promoting private investment in local roads, water management and storage infrastructure.

Development of the financial sector. Regulation of the financial flows into agriculture, competition within the banking sector, functioning capital markets, instruments for risk reduction, access to credit for local farmers and small and medium-sized enterprises, guarantee mechanisms and insurance mechanisms for smallholders upon receipt loans and business development services for local farmers.

Taxation. Tax policies that promote investment in agriculture, appropriate tax burden on the agro-industry, transparent and effective tax policies and administration, coordination of the activities of central and local tax authorities.

Government policies and market interventions can have a major impact on the agricultural investment climate and especially on the economic incentives to invest in the sector. Some government actions are relevant to all sectors or the economy as a whole.

The main agricultural-specific policies affecting agricultural incentives include tariffs, input subsidies and credit, price controls, quantitative restrictions on trade, government spending, and taxes. There may also be indirect impacts on agriculture through policies such as protectionism towards other sectors, exchange rates and interest rates, fiscal and monetary policies. Such policies can have a significant impact on incentives to invest in agriculture relative to other sectors.

References:

1. Analiticheski doklad Sovershenstvovanie organizatsionno-pravovykh uslovii po privilecheniyu inostrannykh investorov v regiony Respubliki Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2015.
2. Investitsii vdali ot tsentra: vygodno li vkladyvat' v regiony? // Informatsion-nyi portal KUN.UZ. URL: <http://kun.uz/ru/news/2017/01/12/investicii-vdali-ot-centra-vygodno-li-vkladyvat-vregiony>
3. Prezident postavil zadachu udvoit' VVP k 2030 godu // Gazeta.UZ. URL: <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2016/01/16/double>
4. Abrams S. A Practical Approach to the International Valuation and Capital Allocation Puzzle. Salomon Smith Barney, 2002.
5. Analytical report "Improvement of organizational and legal conditions for attracting foreign investors to the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan". Tashkent: UNDP Uzbekistan, 2015.
6. Bruner R. et al. (). Introduction to "Valuation in Emerging Markets" // Emerging Markets Review. 2002. №3. DOI: 10.1016/S1566-0141(02)00039-0